

MEDIN Change Log 28 October 2022

This document is a log of changes that have been implemented while incrementing the MEDIN Discovery Metadata Standard Guidance Notes from v3.1.1 to v3.1.2. The changes were necessary to update NERC vocabulary server and ISO Codelist URLs and to make correction edits to XML examples for some elements.

The full list of changes is as follows. These are ordered approximately by the location they appear in the Guidance Notes document.

- Minor typographic, XML and formatting errors corrected throughout the document to account for grammatical/spelling mistakes, XML errors (e.g., missing '/' in closure tags) and formatting inconsistencies respectively.
- Section 4 - Filling in an element ((i) Example XML fragment): Text amendment to indicate that a mapping of the MEDIN elements to the ISO 19115 and UK GEMINI 2.3 elements has been added in Annex A.
- Element - 4 Resource Type: updated link to FAQs on the MEDIN website to use the current URL.
- Amended the ISO codelist links throughout the Guidance Notes to use the updated URL.
- Element 31 - Hierarchy level name: gmd:identificationInfo and gmd:MD_DataIdentification XML tags removed from element's example XML fragments to be consistent with other elements that do not have XML tags nested within the gmd:identificationInfo XML block.
- Updated NERC Vocabulary Server URLs for each controlled vocabulary library throughout the document to use the current URL.
- Element 32 - Spatial representation type: added text to include specific Spatial representation type codes that GEMINI specify are to be used: 'Codes to be used are 'vector', 'grid', 'tin' and/or 'textTable'. This follows guidance from GEMINI.
- Element - 11 Keywords (Keywords for Services): Link to Spatial Data Services Category Codelist as defined in Part D 4 of the Metadata Implementing Rules added to guidance text and '*Example XML fragment for service keyword from part D4 of the INSPIRE Metadata Implementing Rules (for metadata for services)*' as a gmx:Anchor.
- Element - 11 Keywords: added missing gmd:thesaurusName XML tags (and nested tags) to '*Example XML fragment showing OAI Harvesting keywords for MEDIN*'.
- Element - 11 Keywords: erroneous </gmd:Extent> and <!-- ... --> XML tags removed and </gmd:MD_DataIdentification> tag added before </gmd:identificationInfo> (correct location) in '*Example XML fragment for vertical extent keywords from controlled vocabulary L13 SeaVox Vertical Co-ordinate Coverages*'.
- Element 15 - Spatial reference system: erroneous </gco:CharacterString> XML tag removed from '*Example XML fragment using Code and controlled vocabulary*'.
- Element 15 - Spatial reference system: Added XML example with OpenGIS coordinate reference system controlled vocabulary as the gmx:Anchor.

- Element 16 - Temporal reference: gco:date XML tags amended to have uppercase 'D' in '*Example XML fragment (for datasets and series of datasets) (publication)*' and in '*Example XML fragment (metadata for services) (publication)*'.
- Element 18 - Spatial resolution: Added ISO TC 211 link to gmxUom.xml (ISO unit of measure codelist) to '*Example XML fragment (for datasets and series of datasets) (Distance) (encoded using ISO unit of measure XML encoding for metre)*'. Previous link was standards.iso.org but gmxUom.xml codelist no longer appears to be available on standards.iso.org.
- Element 21 - Conditions applying for access and use: gmd:MD_Metadata, gmd:identificationInfo and gmd:MD_DataIdentification XML tags added to two example XML fragments to ensure consistency with the other example XML fragments.
- Annex A: added MEDIN GitHub link to mapping of MEDIN v3.1.2 to ISO 19115 and UK GEMINI 2.3 standards (https://github.com/medin-marine/Discovery-Standard-public-content/tree/main/Guidance_notes/MEDIN_GEMINI_INSPIRE_Mapping).
- Added codelist links to Annexes G, H, I, L, M and N for ISO Restriction, ISO Responsible party, ISO Frequency of maintenance, ISO CI_OnlineFunction, ISO Spatial representation type and ISO Character set respectively to enable user to refer to most up to date list.
- Annex J: added missing INSPIRE theme ('Geographical names') to Keyword list.